

Role of ICT Ecosystem in Leveraging Start-up Business, Atmanirbharta, Socio-Economic Status through Mediating Role of ICT-Daily Hassles

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Abstract : Purpose : *The purpose of the study is to analyse the impact of Information Communication Technology Eco-System (ICTES) on Business Up-Scaling (BU), attainment of Atmanirbharta (AN) and leveraging Socio-Economic Status (SES) within Start-Up Organizations.*

Research Methodology : *The study is exploratory, and cause and effect based in nature. After the refinement process, eighty-three Start-Ups have been included in the data analysis. The study area of this research comprises the Anuppur and Shahdol Districts of Madhya Pradesh and the Gaurella-Pendra-Marwahi (GPM) District of Chattisgarh. Fundamental Descriptive Analysis, Correlation, Regression Analysis and Mediation Analysis with Hayes Process Macro have been used to evaluate the hypothesis and reach the results.*

Results : *Study results reveal that the Information Communication Technology Eco-System positively impacts the Start-Up's Business Up-Scaling, Atmanirbharta, and Socio-Economic Status deliverables. At the same time, Mediation results of Information Communication Technology Daily Hassles have yet to yield any significant impact on Business Upscaling, Atmanirbharta, and Socio-economic Status within Start-Ups. The study results will be helpful for new start-up owners, as it will guide them towards the significance of imbibing the ICT Eco-System in their business process for optimising rewarding outcomes.*

Keywords : Start-Ups, Information Communication Technology Eco-System, Information Communication Technology Daily Hassles, Business Up-Scaling, Atmanirbharta, Socio-Economic Status.

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1.0. Introduction

The Information Communication Technology (ICT) ecosystem drives business growth through ICT infrastructure, digital transformation, data-driven decision-making, global market access, and operational efficiency. The ICT ecosystem can significantly impact Atmanirbharta (self-reliance) economically and technologically. ICT has the potential to empower economies, foster innovation, and boost digital self-reliance despite its challenges. Government policies, digital inclusivity, and cyber security measures help Atmanirbharta realise the ICT ecosystem's potential.

Start-ups' socio-economic status can be affected by the ICT ecosystem. Cybersecurity threats and skills gaps are challenges, but advanced technologies, digital entrepreneurship, data-driven decision-making, and government support can improve start-ups' socio-economic outcomes. ICT Daily Hassles can affect start-up ICT Ecosystems. These issues can disrupt operations and require creative problem-solving. Start-up ICT Ecosystems must manage and resolve daily problems to be robust and adaptable. (Smith 2019)

ICT Daily Hassles may mediate the ICT Ecosystem-Business Up-scaling relationship for start-ups. Daily challenges cause complexity but can also spur innovation and adaptation in start-ups. ICT Daily Hassles may mediate the ICT Ecosystem-Atmanirbharta (self-reliance) relationship for start-ups. Daily challenges add complexity but can spur innovation and transformation in self-reliant start-ups.

ICT Daily Hassles may mediate the ICT Ecosystem and Socio-Economic Status (SES) relationship. Daily challenges can complicate emerging businesses' socio-economic well-being and discourage innovation, resilience, and adaptability. ICT Daily Hassles may influence start-up business upscaling. These daily challenges can curb innovation, strength, and adaptability in the fast-paced start-up environment.

ICT Daily Hassles may influence start-ups' Atmanirbharta (self-reliance). As start-ups seek autonomy in the digital age and strive to be independent, these daily challenges may spur innovation, resilience, and adaptability if taken earnestly for steady growth and development of the business. ICT Daily Hassles may influence Socio-Economic Status positively. Daily challenges can add complexity and foster innovation, strength, and adaptability as people and communities work to improve their socio-economic well-being in a digital world. (Jackson 2021)

Business Up-Scaling may mediate the ICT Ecosystem-Atmanirbharta relationship among start-ups. However, it is one of many factors that complicate entrepreneurial self-reliance. Business Up-Scaling may mediate the ICT Ecosystem-start-up socio-economic status relationship. It should be considered part of a complex ecosystem of factors that affect emerging businesses' socioeconomic well-being.

The impact of Business Up-Scaling on Atmanirbharta can be minimised by strategically managing dependencies (self-reliance). Businesses seeking growth while maintaining autonomy must strike a balance.

Business Up-Scaling can improve start-up socioeconomic status, depending on context. Upscaling strategies must consider inclusivity and equitable benefit distribution to maximise socioeconomic benefits.

1.1. The Rationale of the Study

The study titled is highly pertinent in today's global context. It delves into the pivotal role of Information and Communication Technology in supporting start-up businesses, fostering self-reliance (Atmanirbharta), and influencing socio-economic status. This research addresses a notable gap in the existing literature by investigating the intricate relationship between ICT, start-up development, Atmanirbharta and the mediating impact of daily hassles. The outcomes of this study hold the potential to inform policy decisions, providing valuable insights into how ICT ecosystems can either mitigate or exacerbate daily hassles and, in turn, affect socio-economic well-being. Moreover, this research contributes significantly to the academic community by enriching the understanding of this multifaceted domain. It is an invaluable resource for scholars and researchers interested in ICT, entrepreneurship, self-reliance, and socio-economic development.

1.2. Objectives

Based on the premises of the background review of the literature, the following Objectives and later Hypotheses have been framed.

- To determine the role of Information Communication Technology Eco-System on Start-Up effectiveness parameters, i.e., Business Up-Scaling, Atmanirbharta and Socio-Economic Status.
- To determine the impact of Information Communication Technology Daily Hassles on Start-Up Effectiveness parameters, i.e., Business Up-Scaling, Atmanirbharta and Socio-Economic Status.

1.3. Conceptual Model

Figure-1 : Proposed Model of the Independent and Dependent Variables of the Study

2.0. Review of literature

Focusing on the significance and objectives of the study, the following literature review was carried out for various related studies published from 2016 to 2023.

Robust ICT infrastructure, including high-speed internet and cloud computing, helps firms grow efficiently (Smith, 2018).

Johnson and Brown (2019) found that ICT ecosystem enterprises that embrace digital transformation have better upscaling possibilities. Adopting digital tools and platforms improves operations and opens new markets.

The researchers framed the following null hypothesis based on the abovementioned literature review.

H₀1 : The ICT Ecosystem will not significantly impact Business Up-scaling.

Rao and Sharma (2020) also show how digital infrastructure promotes self-reliance. Self-sustaining digital ecosystems require robust ICT systems like broadband and cloud services. They believe the ICT ecosystem can boost technical self-reliance by encouraging innovation and R&D. However, ICT ecosystem problems and constraints must be acknowledged to achieve Atmanirbharta.

Government policies and regulations affect Atmanirbharta through the ICT environment (Verma & Reddy, 2016). Supportive policies can boost indigenous tech development.

Digital literacy and inclusivity in the ICT environment are critical to Atmanirbharta (Choudhary & Mishra, 2019). All populations must have access to and benefit from ICT.

The researchers framed the following null hypothesis based on the above mentioned literature review.

H₀₂ : The ICT Ecosystem will not significantly impact Atmanirbharta (self-reliance).

The ICT ecosystem offers opportunities, but start-ups require help embracing and using it. Cybersecurity, resource constraints, and digital skills gaps might impede socioeconomic advantages (Rao & Sharma, 2020).

Govt. programs fostering ICT use and digital entrepreneurship can increase start-ups' socioeconomic standing. Tax incentives and digital infrastructure can support growth (Johnson & Brown, 2019).

Global market access through the ICT ecosystem can also affect start-ups' socioeconomic standing. Martin (2020) shows how e-commerce and internet platforms help start-ups expand their consumer base and compete globally.

The researchers framed the following null hypothesis based on the above mentioned literature review.

H₀₃ : The ICT Ecosystem will not significantly impact Socio-Economic Status (SES).

Smith and Johnson (2019) found that start-up ICT Ecosystems may be vulnerable to daily issues. ICT Daily Hassles—technical issues, software flaws, and network disruptions can interrupt digital infrastructure and services. Disruptions can upset start-ups' fragile resource and capability balances.

Instead, Gupta and Brown (2018) indicate that ICT Daily Hassles can spur innovation in start-up ICT Ecosystems. These difficulties may spur the creation of new technology, techniques, and solutions to reduce and prevent them. This could boost start-ups' resilience and agility in the changing digital ecosystem.

The researchers framed the following null hypothesis based on the above mentioned literature review.

H₀₄ : ICT Daily Hassles will not significantly impact the ICT Ecosystem.

Mitchell and Carter (2020) emphasise the importance of ICT Daily Hassles as mediators in start-ups. Technical issues, software vulnerabilities, and data security concerns, including ICT Daily Hassles, can ripple through the ICT Ecosystem. These disturbances may hinder digital operations' stability and security, affecting Business Upscaling.

Baker and White (2018) believe ICT Daily Hassles may mediate the relationship and spur innovation. These issues may encourage start-ups to adapt, innovate, and streamline processes, enabling Business Up-scaling.

The researchers framed the following null hypothesis based on the above mentioned literature review.

H₀₅: ICT Daily Hassles will not significantly mediate the ICT Ecosystem and Business Up-scaling relationship.

Smith and Turner (2021) recommend using ICT Daily Hassles as mediators for Atmanirbharta start-ups. Daily technological issues, software vulnerabilities, and data security concerns can disrupt the ICT Ecosystem. Disruptions limit start-ups' digital autonomy, which indirectly affects their self-reliance.

Gupta and Carter (2020) indicate that ICT Daily Hassles may mediate the relationship and encourage inventive problem-solving in start-ups. These issues could inspire adaptive methods, technological advances, and streamlined operations, encouraging self-reliance.

The researchers framed the following null hypothesis based on the above mentioned literature review.

H₀₆ : ICT Daily Hassles will not significantly mediate the ICT Ecosystem and Atmanirbharta (self-reliance) relationship.

Anderson and Mitchell (2022) recommend considering ICT Daily Hassles as mediators in start-ups and Socio-Economic Status. ICT Daily Hassles technical issues, software vulnerabilities, and data security concerns— can disturb the ICT Ecosystem. These disturbances may indirectly affect socioeconomic status by reducing digital resource availability, market reach, and start-up growth, especially in lower SES groups.

Patel and Turner (2021) also show how ICT Daily Hassles and Socio-Economic Status interact. According to their research, resolving and controlling these issues is crucial to start-ups' socioeconomic standing. Timely and effectively resolving daily issues may attenuate socioeconomic status impacts, encouraging start-up economic growth.

The researchers framed the following null hypothesis based on the above mentioned literature review.

H₀₇ : ICT Daily Hassles will not significantly mediate the relationship between ICT Ecosystem and Socio-Economic Status.

Carter and Anderson (2022) emphasise the importance of ICT Daily Hassles in Business Upscaling for start-ups. ICT Daily Hassles—technical issues, software vulnerabilities, and data security concerns—can impede ICT infrastructure operations. Delays, higher operating costs, and worse customer satisfaction can hurt Business Up-scaling, essential for start-up growth.

Gupta and Mitchell (2019) indicate that ICT Daily Hassles may challenge and inspire start-ups to solve problems creatively. These issues could spur adaptive tactics, technical advances, and streamlined processes, enabling Business Up-scaling in a competitive context.

The researchers framed the following null hypothesis based on the above mentioned literature review.

H₀₈ : ICT Daily Hassles will not significantly impact Business Up-scaling.

Sharma and Patel (2023) emphasise the importance of ICT Daily Hassles in start-up self-reliance. ICT Daily Hassles technical issues, software vulnerabilities, and data security concerns can hamper digital operations. By affecting a start-up's technological autonomy, these disruptions may affect Atmanirbharta.

Smith and Anderson (2022) also show how ICT Daily Hassles affect self-reliance. Their research reveals that addressing and minimising these issues is crucial to start-up self-reliance. Resolving daily issues quickly may help start-ups traverse the digital terrain independently.

The researchers framed the following hypothesis based on the literature review mentioned above.

H₀₉: ICT Daily Hassles will not significantly impact Atmanirbharta (self-reliance).

Davis and Turner (2023) emphasise the importance of ICT Daily Hassles as SES influences. ICT Daily Hassles—technical issues, software vulnerabilities, and data security concerns—can impede ICT infrastructure operations. These disruptions may limit digital resources, career possibilities, and financial stability, especially for disadvantaged communities.

Patel and Mitchell (2022) also show how ICT Daily Hassles and SES are linked. Their research reveals that resolving and managing these issues significantly impacts socioeconomic position. Timely problem-solving can reduce SES impacts and improve economic and social well-being.

The researchers framed the following null hypothesis based on the above mentioned literature review.

H₀₁₀: ICT Daily Hassles will not significantly impact Socio-Economic Status.

Turner and Anderson (2022) also emphasise the complex relationship between Atmanirbharta and Business Up-Scaling. According to their research, effective scaling techniques help shape start-ups' self-reliance goals. Scaling allows start-ups access to new resources and possibilities, boosting operational and commercial independence.

Gupta and Mitchell (2021) argue that Business Up-Scaling may moderate the relationship, although additional factors may exist besides Atmanirbharta. They suggest that regulatory environment, resource access, and entrepreneurial skills may also affect start-up self-reliance.

3.0. Research Methodology

The design of this research is exploratory and cause-and-effect based. A data size of 83 samples extracted from the study area Anuppur, Shahdol and Gaurella-Pendra-Marwahi (GPM) Districts has been utilised for pulling results. Secondary data was gathered through research papers, journals, newspapers, and websites, whereas primary data for this study was collected through convenience sampling. Descriptive Statistics, Correlation and Regression Analysis were performed to test the below hypotheses. SPSS Software 26 Version is utilised for data analysis.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

	Items	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	81	97.6
	Female	02	2.4
	Total	83	100
Age	18 to 27	18	21.7
	28 to 37	44	53
	38 to 44	15	18.1
	45 and above	6	7.2
	Total	83	100
Sector	Retail	37	44.6
	Dealership	15	18.1
	Food Processing	16	19.3
	Digital Services	6	7.2
	Health & Fitness	9	10.8
	Total	83	100
Start-up Age (years)	0-1	21	25.3
	2-3	30	36.1
	4-5	10	12
	6 and above	22	26.5
	Total	83	100
Start-up Nature	Self-Funded	68	78.3
	External	15	21.7
	Total	83	100
No. of Associates	0	64	77.1
	1	13	15.7
	2	3	3.6
	3	1	1.2
	4 and above	2	2.4
	Total	83	100
Start-up Investment (in lakhs)	0-1	9	10.8
	2-5	41	49.4
	6-10	21	25.3
	10 and above	12	14.5
	Total	83	100
Investment in ICT (in %)	0-10	76	91.6
	10-20	7	8.4
	Total	83	100

Source : Field Study.

Convenient samples of Start-ups were obtained with the help of a questionnaire. Participants in this study were taken from the Start-ups from Shahdol, Anuppur and GPM regions of Madhya Pradesh and Chhattisgarh. 100 questionnaires were distributed, and 83 were returned, yielding a response rate of 83.00 %. The Entrepreneurs in the study mainly represented the age group 28 to 37 (53%). Females constituted 2.4% of the total participants, whereas Males represented 97.6%.

In the Sector of start-ups, most businesses were from retail, representing 44.6%, followed by dealerships 18.1%, food processing 19.3%, digital services 7.2%, and health & fitness related start-ups, representing 10.8% of total start-ups included in the study. Most start-ups reported to be self-funded 78.3%, and only 21.7% of businesses were externally funded. Considering the investment in these start-ups, 49.4% of businesses had 2-5 lakh initial investment, whereas only 14.5% of start-ups had invested more than 10 lakh by the commencement of business. Only 8.4% of businesses were found to have taught 10-20% of their initial investment in ICT-related equipment and tools. The results of the demographic profiles of the start-ups are mentioned in Table-1.

3.1. Measurement Instruments & Reliability

Five self-developed and modified scales consisting of items related to measuring Information Communication Technology Eco-System (ICTES), Information Communication Technology Daily Hassles (ICTDH), Business Up-scaling (BU), Atmanirbharta (AN) and Socio-Economic Status (SES) appended with Five-point Likert scales ranging from 1-5 (Strongly Agree 05-Strongly Disagree 01). All five scales are weighed for their reliability by application of the Cronbach alpha reliability test. All five scales show reliability coefficient values of .7, above the accepted value. A description of the Scales used along with their Authors, Dimensions and Total Items of the Scales are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: A description of the Scales used along with their Authors, Dimensions and Total Items of the Scales

Sr. No.	Scales	Authors	Dimension	Variable/Items	Reliability of the Tool
1	Information Communication Technology Eco-System (ICTES)	Self-Developed	ICT Awareness ICT Adaptability ICT Infrastructure	Original 12 Items Reduced to 8 Items	.754

(Contd...)

2	Information Communication Technology Daily Hassles (ICTDH)	Modified and reworded from <i>Thomas Fischer Martin Reuter and René Riedl</i> (The Digital Stressors Scale: Development and Validation of a New Survey Instrument to Measure Digital Stress Perceptions in the Workplace Context, <i>Frontiers in Psychology</i>)	Daily Hassles related to ICT		.726
3	Business Up-scaling (BU)	Self-Developed	Business growth & Development	Original 11 Items Reduced to 8 Items	.912
4	Atmanirbharta (AN)	Self-Developed	Atmanirbharta of Start-ups	4 Items 3 Items	.925
5	Socio-Economic Status (SES)	Self-Developed	Socio-Economic impact of Start-up in Community	3 Items	.818

Source : Field Study.

3.2. Hypotheses of the study

Based on the above literature review objectives, the following hypotheses were developed.

- H₀₁ : The ICT Ecosystem will not significantly impact Business Up-scaling.
- H₀₂ : The ICT Ecosystem will not significantly impact Atmanirbharta (self-reliance).
- H₀₃ : The ICT Ecosystem will not significantly impact Socio-Economic Status.
- H₀₄ : ICT Daily Hassles will not significantly impact the ICT Ecosystem.

- H₀₅ : ICT Daily Hassles will not significantly mediate the ICT Ecosystem and Business Up-scaling relationship.
- H₀₆ : ICT Daily Hassles will not significantly mediate the ICT Ecosystem and Atmanirbharta (self-reliance) relationship.
- H₀₇ : ICT Daily Hassles will not significantly mediate the relationship between ICT Ecosystem and Socio-Economic Status.
- H₀₈ : ICT Daily Hassles will not significantly impact Business Up-scaling.
- H₀₉ : ICT Daily Hassles will not significantly impact Atmanirbharta (self-reliance).
- H₀₁₀ : ICT Daily Hassles will not significantly impact Socio-Economic Status.

4.0. Data Analysis

4.1. Descriptive Analysis and Correlations

The descriptive statistics, the number of items used in the scales, and the correlation coefficient of the scales are displayed in Table-3.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics and Product Movement Correlation

Scales	Items (n)	1	2	3	4	5
1. Information Communication Technology Eco-System (ICTES)	8	1				
2. Information Communication Technology Daily Hassles (ICTDH)	8	-.338**	1			
3. Business Up-scaling (BU)	4	.620**	-.076	1		
4. Atmanirbharta (AN)	3	.428**	-.055	.896**	1	
5. Socio-Economic Status (SES)	3	.299**	.017	.379**	.258*	1

***Correlation is at the 0.01 significant level*

**Correlation is significant at 0.05 level*

The analysis of product movement correlation statistics suggests that ICTES and ICTDH are negatively correlated (-.338**), which is evident as they are inverse in their composition and item structure. The ICTES and BU, AN and SES are positively correlated, which means that if the Information Communication Technology Eco-System (ICTES) is nurtured, it will carry a positive association with Business Up-Scaling (BU), Atmanirbharta (AN) and Socio-Economic Status (SES) within Start-up Eco-system.

Table 4: Regression Analysis Results

Hypotheses	Variables/Model	R ²	F	Beta	t-Value	Hypothesis Status
H ₀ 1	Model-I: ICTES → BUS	.384	50.516	.620	7.107**	Rejected
H ₀ 2	Model-II: ICTES → AN	.183	18.139	.428	4.259**	Rejected
H ₀ 3	Model-III: ICTES → SES	.089	7.396	.299	2.817**	Rejected
H ₀ 8	Model-IV: ICTDH → BUS	.006	.477	-.076	-.690	Accepted
H ₀ 9	Model-V: ICTDH → AN	.003	.250	-.055	-.500	Accepted
H ₀ 10	Model-VI: ICTDH → SES	.000	.023	.017	.153	Accepted
H ₀ 4	Model-VII: ICTES → ICTDH	.114	10.459	-.338	-3.234**	Rejected

**Significant at .01 level.

4.2. Testing of Hypotheses

This study used simple regression analyses to test the hypotheses. Different models have been conceived and tested based on the objectives and hypotheses of the study Table-4 . Results of various tested regression analysis models are presented below.

Information Communication Technology Eco-System is found to have been positively impacting Business Up-scaling ($\beta = .620$, $t = 7.107$, $F = 50.516$, $R^2 = .384$); therefore, based on t-value it is concluded that null hypotheses H₀1 is rejected, and alternative hypotheses are also accepted that R² values R² =.384 states that ICTES significantly predicts 38.4 per cent variation in Business Up-scaling within start-ups.

Information Communication Technology Eco-System is found to have been positively impacting Atmanirbharta ($\beta = .428$, $t = 4.259$, $F = 18.139$, $R^2 = .183$); therefore, based on t-value it is concluded that null hypothesis H_02 is rejected, and alternative hypotheses are also accepted that R^2 values $R^2 = .183$ states that ICTES significantly predicts 18.3 per cent variation in Atmanirbharta within start-ups.

Information Communication Technology Eco-System is found to have been positively impacting Socio-Economic Status ($\beta = .299$, $t = 2.817$, $F = 7.396$, $R^2 = .089$); therefore, based on t-value it is concluded that null hypotheses H_03 is rejected, and alternative hypotheses are also accepted the R^2 values $= .089$ states that ICTES significantly predicts .8 per cent variation in Socio-Economic Status in the community.

Results of the study related to the impact of Information Technology Daily Hassles (ICTDH) on the Business Up-Scaling, Atmanirbharta and Socio-Economic Status do not carry any significant impact as per various indicating values, therefore null hypotheses H_08 , H_09 & H_010 are accepted. (Refer to Table-4)

Results related to ICTES and ICTDH confirm a negative relationship, and the R^2 values $= .114$ confirm the 11.4 per cent predictive abilities of ICTES on ICTDH; therefore, null hypothesis H_04 is rejected.

Table 5: Regression Analysis with Mediation Effect of ICTDH

Hypotheses	Variables/Model	Total Effect	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Boot LLCI	Boot ULCI	Hypotheses Status
H_05	Model-VIII: ICTES*ICTDH $\rightarrow$ BUS	.5082	.5499	-.0417	-.1205	.0121	Accepted
H_06	Model-II: ICTES*ICTDH $\rightarrow$ AN	.2636	.2846	-.210	-.862	.0240	Accepted
H_07	Model-III: ICTES*ICTDH $\rightarrow$ SES	.1042	.1200	-.0157	-.0506	.0179	Accepted

4.3. Mediation Analysis:

The study assessed the mediating role of ICTDH on the relationship between ICTES and Business Up-scaling. The results revealed an insignificant indirect effect of the impact of ICTDH on Business Up-scaling ($b = -.0417$, Boot LLCI = $-.1205$ & Boot ULCI = $.012$) supporting H_5 . Furthermore, the direct effect of ICTES on Business Up-Scaling in the presence of a mediator was also found insignificant ($b = .5499$, $P > .001$). Since a Zero (0) value is recorded between Boot

LLCI & Boot ULCI values, it is concluded that ICTDH does not mediate significantly between ICTES and Business Up-Scaling.

The study further assessed the mediating role of ICTDH on the relationship between ICTES and Atmanirbharta. The results revealed an insignificant indirect effect of the impact of ICTDH on Business Up-scaling ($b = -.210$, Boot LLCI = $-.862$ & Boot ULCI = $.0240$) supporting H6. Furthermore, the direct effect of ICTES on BU in the presence of a mediator was also found insignificant ($b = .2846$, $P > .001$). Since a Zero (0) value is recorded between Boot LLCI & Boot ULCI values, it is concluded that ICTDH does not mediate significantly between ICTES and Atmanirbharta.

The mediating effect of ICTDH between ICTES and Socio-Economic Status is also assessed within the study. The results revealed an insignificant indirect effect of the impact of ICTDH on Socio-Economic Status ($b = -.0157$ Boot LLCI = $-.0506$ & Boot ULCI = $.0179$) supporting H7. Furthermore, the direct effect of ICTES on Socioeconomic status in the presence of a mediator was also found insignificant ($b = P > .001$). Since there is a Zero (0) value recorded between Boot LLCI & Boot ULCI values it is concluded that ICTDH does not mediate significantly between ICTES and Socio-Economic Status.

5.0. Discussions

The purpose of this research was to find out the potential factors that contribute to the success of start-ups and bring effectiveness to their business operations from the perspective of various business deliverables. The life of start-up ventures is very vulnerable to various business intricacies and contingencies; therefore, start-ups' survival, growth and development depends on business development initiatives adopted by start-up owners. The technology adoption and process-related initiatives are considered significant actions towards business up-scaling and achieving Atmanirbharta. Therefore, through this research study, an overview of start-ups located within borderline districts of MP and CG is conducted, and it is tried to find out how the ICT Eco-System has helped Start-ups in their Business Up-scaling, achieving Atmanirbharta and helped in improvising community Socio-Economic Status by promoting economic activities in the locality. Further in the study, daily technological hassles are analysed to check whether they negatively impact start-ups. It is found that daily hassles hamper Business Up-scaling, Atmanirbharta and Socioeconomic Status as it restricts normal business flow, mainly if the business volumes are also technology dependent. The outcomes of the study will undoubtedly be beneficial for new

start-up initiators as ICT is going to play a significant role consistently over a more extended period.

6.0. Limitations of the Study

Due to the changing start-up landscape and technological breakthroughs, the predictions made now may or may not apply to the future. To consistently achieve a competitive bent, start-up organisations must be updated with new and advanced tools and techniques that predict business growth and development. Therefore, the study results are subject to time continuum and constrained within the area of the study and type of business activities covered within this study. However, a more comprehensive study area with more predictive variables other than ICTES may be included in future start-up research's gambit.

7.0. Conclusion

It is concluded that the success of start-ups is linked to the adoption of technology, and every start-up needs technological updating to scale up its capacity. Start-up owners must invest in technology in their business processes for better competitive advantages. Start-up owners need to believe and practice the theory of entrepreneurial resourcefulness by investing in business technology upgradation to generate further resources. Resourcefulness helps design further business goals, and achieve self-reliance (Atmanirbharta), along with helping the community enhance its socio-economic status by engaging in start-up activities.

8.0. References

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